

THE COURSE OF CYCLISATION OF α -BENZYLHOMOPHTHALIC ACIDS.
PART II. A SYNTHESIS OF INDENO-(3':2'-3:4)ISO-COUMARIN

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Cyclisation of several substituted benzylhomophthalic acids led only to indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarins. A synthesis of indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin is described. Several reactions of the isocoumarin have been studied including its conversion into isobenzopyrylium salts.

In the previous communication it has been shown that the cyclisations of α -benzylhomophthalic acids (α -*o*-carboxyphenyl-phenylpropionic acids) lead either to a seven-membered ring ketone or to an indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin or to a mixture of the both (Chatterjea and Mukherjee, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 379). We have now studied the cyclisations in several other cases (I-VI) by varying substituents in either of the rings. In all the cases, now studied, the formation of the indenoisocoumarin resulted, showing that the five-membered ring ketone was formed in preference to a seven-membered one. Therefore the formation of dibenzotropone derivatives by the cyclisation of 3:4-dimethoxybenzyl- or 3:4-diethoxybenzyl-homophthalic acid is an exception to the above generalisation.

(VII)

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| (I) R' = Me ; R = R'' = R''' = H. | (IV) R = Me ; R' = R'' = R''' = H. |
| (II) R' = Cl ; R = R'' = R''' = H. | (V) R = R' = R'' = H ; R''' = Me. |
| (III) R' = OMe ; R = R'' = R''' = H. | (VI) R = R' = R'' = R''' = OMe. |

An unequivocal synthesis of the indenoisocoumarin (VII : R = R' = R'' = R''' = H) establishes its structure. The synthesis started from phthalaldehydic acid which could not, however, be condensed with homophthalic anhydride by the Perkin synthesis. On the Stobbe condensation with diethyl homophthalate, the half-ester (VIII : R = Et) was readily obtained, which was directly hydrolysed to the acid (VIII : R = H). This acid, best purified by way of its anhydride (by treatment with acetic anhydride), was reduced with sodium amalgam to the tricarboxylic acid (IX). This on boiling with acetic anhydride afforded a quantitative yield of indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin.

The dicarboxylic acid (X) was similarly obtained from phthalaldehydic acid, and ethyl phenylacetate. Although this acid could not so far be cyclised by polyphosphoric acid to a seven-membered ketone (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*), it readily afforded 2-phenylindan-1-one on boiling with acetic anhydride, and thus validating the synthesis of the indenoisocoumarin, mentioned above. The UV absorption spectra of a few indenoisocoumarins are recorded in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

Indenoisocoumarin readily reacted with two moles of Grignard's reagent (methylmagnesium iodide or phenylmagnesium bromide) to furnish excellent yields of indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isochromenes (XI: R = Me or Ph) (cf. Colonge and Boisse, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1956, 1337). On treatment with one mole of phenylmagnesium bromide the related carbinol base became isolable; this on treatment with perchloric acid yielded the isobenzopyrylium perchlorate (XIII) (cf. Shriner *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, 13, 477). On reduction with lithium aluminium hydride the isocoumarin afforded

the isochromene (XI: R=H) directly (cf. Chatterjea, *Chem. Ber.*, 1958, 91, 2636). This compound provided the pyrylium salt (XIV) on treatment with triphenylmethyl perchlorate. The UV absorption spectra of the isochromenes are recorded in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

Reduction of the indenoisocoumarin (VII: $R=R'=R''=R'''=H$) with sodium borohydride in absolute methanol afforded a diol. The analysis fits $C_{16}H_{16}O_2$. The compound has weak absorption in the ultraviolet and is identified as (XII). This structure is confirmed as the compound is also formed by the lithium aluminium hydride reduction of 2-*o*-carboxyphenylindan-1-one.

* EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 4-Methylhomophthalic Acid.—This acid was prepared from 6-methylindan-1-one by the standard procedure. The ketone was prepared according to Miller and Rhode (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1898). The phenylsemicarbazone crystallised from ethanol in yellowish white, woolly needles, m.p. 225°.

To a solution of the indanone (2 g.) in ethanol (12 c.c.) was added amyl nitrite (4 g.) and HCl (conc., 0.5 c.c.). The mixture was maintained at 40-50° for 20 minutes when 2-oximino-6-methylindan-1-one separated (1.7 g.). This crystallised from ethanol in colorless plates, m.p. 217°. (Found: C, 68.3; H, 4.7. $C_{10}H_8O_2N$ requires C, 68.6; H, 5.2%).

p-Toluenesulphonyl chloride (3 g.) was added to the yellow solution of the aforementioned oximino compound (2 g.) in 10% aqueous NaOH (21 c.c.) and the mixture heated to 100° in the course of 10 minutes with agitation, and then kept at that temperature for further 10 minutes. The cooled solution was treated with charcoal, filtered and acidified with HCl, yielding *p*-tolylacetoneitrile-5-carboxylic acid (1 g.), which crystallised from water as yellowish white needles, m.p. 208°. (Found: C, 69.0; H, 5.4. $C_{10}H_8O_2N$ requires C, 68.6; H, 5.2%).

Hydrolysis of this nitrile (6 g.) was effected by boiling with 20% aqueous NaOH (60 c.c.) for 14 hours. Acidification with 33% H_2SO_4 afforded 4-methylhomophthalic acid (3.5 g.) crystallising from water in colorless prisms, m.p. 213°. (Found: C, 62.2; H, 5.4. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 61.9; H, 6.3%). Esterification with dry methanol and sulphuric acid in the usual manner yielded the *dimethyl ester*, b.p. 155-60°/160 mm. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 6.6. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 64.9; H, 6.3%).

α -3-Methylbenzylidenehomophthalic Acid.—A mixture of *m*-methylbenzaldehyde (4 g.), homophthalic acid (6 g.), fused sodium acetate (2.7 g.), and acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) was heated in an oil bath at 150° for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled, decomposed with water and heated with dilute NaOH solution (50 c.c., 10%) on the steam bath for 1 hour until all soluble matter went into solution. The mixture was then filtered from the insoluble residue, cooled and acidified. The acid crystallised from acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 210° with previous sintering due to anhydride formation. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0%). The properties and analyses of other α -benzylidenehomophthalic acids are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

α -Benzylidenehomophthalic acids.

	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1. α -3-Chlorobenzylidene-	203°	Colorless prisms	$C_{16}H_{11}O_4Cl$	C: 63.6% H: 3.8	63.5% 3.7
2. α -3-Methoxybenzylidene-	215-16°	Do	$C_{17}H_{14}O_5$	C: 60.6 H: 5.0	68.5 4.7
3. α -4-Methylbenzylidene-	231-32°	Yellowish plates	$C_{17}H_{14}O_4$	C: 72.5 H: 5.3	72.3 5.0
4. α -Benzylidene-4-methyl-	209°	Colorless plates	$C_{17}H_{14}O_4$	C: 72.5 H: 5.2	72.3 5.0
5. α -Veratrylidene-4:5-dimethoxy-	241-42°	Colorless prisms	$C_{20}H_{16}O_5$	C: 62.1 H: 5.5	61.8 5.2

* All m.p.'s are uncorrected. The absorption spectra were measured in a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, D.U. model.

α -3-Methylbenzylhomophthalic Acid.—The foregoing acid (4 g.), dissolved in minimum quantity of NaOH, was treated with sodium amalgam (200 g., 2%). After 48 hours the alkaline solution was separated and acidified to afford the acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 184° (gas evolution), yield quantitative. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 5.8. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.7%). The properties and analyses of other α -benzylhomophthalic acids are shown in Table II.

TABLE II
 α -Benzylhomophthalic acids.

	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1. α -3-Chlorobenzyl-	183°	Creamy prisms	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4Cl$	C: 63.1% H: 4.5	63.1% 4.3
2. α -3-Methoxybenzyl-	151	Colorless prisms	$C_{17}H_{14}O_5$	C: 68.3 H: 5.5	68.0 5.4
3. α -4-Methylbenzyl-	175-76°	Colorless plates	$C_{17}H_{16}O_4$	C: 72.0 H: 5.8	71.8 5.7
4. α -Benzyl-4-methyl-	188-89°	Do	$C_{17}H_{16}O_4$	C: 72.0 H: 5.9	71.8 5.7
5. α -Veratryl-4: 5-dimethoxy-	194-95°	Do	$C_{20}H_{18}O_4$	C: 61.5 H: 5.8	61.5 5.7

6'-Methylindeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin (VII: $R' = Me$; $R = R'' = R''' = H$).—The above reduced acid (0.2 g.) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (10 g.) for 12 hours at 100° when a brownish fluorescent solution resulted. The mixture was then poured into crushed ice and the precipitated solid collected, washed with dilute alkali, and crystallised from acetic acid. The compound crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish prisms, m.p. 166° (with previous sintering) raised to 178-79° by chromatography on alumina in benzene solution. The substance dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.) forming a yellow solution with a brilliant green fluorescence. (Found: C, 81.8; H, 4.7. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 82.2; H, 4.9%). The properties and analyses of other indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarins are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III
Indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarins (VII).

	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Halo-chromy in H_2SO_4 .	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1. $R' = Cl$, $R = R'' = R''' = H$.	212°	Yellowish needles	Brilliant green fluorescence	$C_{16}H_8O_4Cl$	C: 71.3% H: 3.2	71.5% 3.4
2. $R' = Me$, $R = R'' = R''' = H$.	188°	Yellowish plates	Do	$C_{17}H_{12}O_3$	C: 77.5 H: 4.7	77.3 4.6
3. $R = OMe$; $R' = R'' = R''' = H$.	186-87°	Lemon-yellow woolly needles	Do	$C_{17}H_{12}O_3$	C: 81.9 H: 4.7	82.2 4.9
4. $R = R' = R'' = H$, $R''' = Me$.	221-22°	Yellowish plates	Do	$C_{17}H_{12}O_3$	C: 82.4 H: 5.0	82.2 4.9
5. $R = R' = R'' = R''' = OMe$.	241-42°	Cream coloured plates	Deep violet colour	$C_{20}H_{16}O_6$	C: 67.6 H: 5.5	67.8 5.1

α -Carboxybenzylhomophthalic Acid (VIII: $R = H$).—A mixture of phthalaldehydic acid (1.5 g.) and dimethyl homophthalate (2.1 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (0.46 g.) in dry

methanol (10 c.c.) and refluxed gently for 24 hours. During this period the sodium salt of the half-ester separated. After removal of ethanol by distillation water was added to the solid residue and the unchanged material removed by extraction with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified with acetic acid and extracted with ether. After removal of the ether the half-ester (VIII: R=Et) was obtained as an oil (2 g.), which was boiled with 10% NaOH solution (10 c.c.) for 7 minutes, and then acidified. The crystalline solid separating was best purified by converting it into the anhydride by boiling with acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) for 5 minutes. The *anhydride* (0.5 g.) of (VIII: R=H) was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 188°. (Found: C, 70.1; H, 3.4. $C_{17}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 69.4; H, 3.4%).

This anhydride on hydrolysis with alkali, followed by acidification, afforded the corresponding *acid*, which on crystallisation from acetic acid separated as a colorless crystalline mass, m.p. 178-80° (with slow evolution of gas). (Found: C, 65.8; H, 3.5. $C_{17}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 65.4; H, 3.9%).

This acid on reduction with sodium amalgam in the usual manner furnished the colorless *tricarboxylic acid* (IX), which separated from acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 195-96° (with evolution of gas). (Found: C, 65.2; H, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 65.0; H, 4.5%).

Indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin (VII: R=R'=R''=R'''=H).—The above tricarboxylic acid (0.1 g.) was boiled with acetic anhydride (0.5 c.c.) for 2 minutes and then cooled. Beautiful cream-coloured plates of the indenoisocoumarin was obtained, m.p. 173-74°, which was identical with the indenoisocoumarin obtained by the double cyclisation of α -benzylhomophthalic acid (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*). The mixed m.p. of the two samples showed no depression. (Found: C, 82.1; H, 4.4. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$: C, 82.0; H, 4.3%).

Condensation of Phthalaldehydic Acid with Ethyl Phenylacetate.—A mixture of purified phthalaldehydic acid (1.5 g.) and ethyl phenylacetate (1.64 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (0.4 g.) in dry methanol (10 c.c.), and the mixture refluxed for 24 hours. After removal of methanol by distillation from the resultant orange-red solution, the solid cake left was dissolved in water and extracted with ether to remove the unchanged material. The aqueous extract was boiled with 10% NaOH solution (10 c.c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, acidified and then boiled further for 15 minutes. The mixture was cooled in an ice bath when a semisolid mass containing orange needles of the *anhydride* of α -*o*-carboxybenzylidenephylacetic acid and the corresponding *acid* was obtained. The former (0.2 g.), separated by sodium bicarbonate solution, crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 255°. (Found: C, 77.1; H, 3.8. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 76.7; H, 4.0%). From the anhydride the corresponding *acid* was prepared in the usual manner by hydrolysis with alkali. The compound crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 185°. (Found: C, 71.9; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5%).

For the preparation of the reduced acid (X; 1-phenyl-2-*o*-carboxyphenylpropionic acid), the entire semisolid mass, mentioned above, was dissolved in alkali and reduced with sodium amalgam (100 g., 2%). The *acid* (X), isolated as usual, solidified after a long time and was obtained from acetic acid in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 193°. (Found: C, 70.8; H, 5.1. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 71.1; H, 5.2%).

The *diacilide*, prepared through the acid chloride, crystallised from acetic acid in silky plates, m.p. 199°. (Found: C, 79.6; H, 5.9; N, 6.8. $C_{28}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 5.9; N, 6.7%).

2-Phenylindan-1-one.—The acid (X) (0.1 g.) was boiled with acetic anhydride (0.2 c.c.) for 3 minutes. On isolation 2-phenylindan-1-one was obtained, identified through the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone; m.p. and mixed m.p., 217-18°.

Indeno-(3':2'-3:4)-1:1-dimethylisochromene (XI: R=Me). — A solution of indeno-(3':2'-3:4)-isocoumarin (0.5 g.) in benzene (4 c.c.) was added to an excess of MeMgI (ca. 3 moles) in ether and refluxed for 4 hours, when a darkish solution was obtained. The solution was decomposed with HCl (dil.) and the ethereal layer on working up afforded a crystalline solid of the *isochromene*, which was very soluble in benzene but crystallised from ethanol in a colorless mass (0.31 g.), m.p. 91°. It develops a bluish colour with H₂SO₄ (conc.). (Found: C, 87.7; H, 6.5. C₁₈H₁₈O requires C, 87.1; H, 6.5%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 238 (log ϵ 4.12), 240 (log ϵ 4.12), 266 (log ϵ 3.57), 296 (log ϵ 3.76) and 344 m μ (log ϵ 4.31).

Indeno-(3':2'-3:4)-1:1-diphenylisochromene (XI: R=Ph) was prepared exactly as above, employing the indenoisocoumarin (0.5 g.). The gummy magnesium salt separating furnished, on working up, a sticky material, which exhibited a green fluorescence in benzene solution. For purification this was chromatographed in benzene solution on alumina. The light yellowish band was eluted with benzene. After removal of the solvent the residue crystallised from a large volume of ethanol. The *isochromene* was obtained in cream-coloured plates (0.5 g.), m.p. 193°. (Found: C, 90.0; H, 5.5. C₂₈H₂₀O requires C, 90.3; H, 5.4%).

Indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isochromene (XI: R=H). — To a suspension of the indenoisocoumarin (0.1 g.) in ether (80 c.c.) an excess of LiAlH₄ (0.1 g.) was added when a colorless complex separated. This was decomposed after 30 minutes with H₂SO₄ (dil.). The reduced material was obtained as a glassy mass which was dissolved in benzene and left overnight in a refrigerator. A small quantity of an unidentified material (ca. 2 mg., m.p. 140°) was separated by filtration and the filtrate concentrated, dissolved in methanol (2 c.c.), and left in the refrigerator. Colorless prisms of the *isochromene* (0.06 g.) that separated was collected and recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 103-104°, exhibiting a green coloration with H₂SO₄, turning fluorescent green after some time. The compound does not contain any active hydrogen. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 240 (log ϵ 4.17), 280 (log ϵ 3.37) and 336 m μ (log ϵ 4.32). (Found: C, 87.5; H, 5.2. C₁₈H₁₂O requires C, 87.2; H, 5.5%).

Indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isobenzopyrylium perchlorate (cf. Bonthrone and Reid, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2773).—A solution of the foregoing *isochromene* (30 mg.) in glacial acetic acid (1.5 c.c.) was boiled with triphenylmethyl perchlorate (0.05 g.) for 2 minutes and the resulting yellowish brown solution was filtered. The *pyrylium salt* separated from the filtrate in brownish yellow crystalline needles, m.p. 197-99° (decomp.). The compound deteriorated appreciably on recrystallisation and was not analysed due to paucity of the material.

Indeno-(3':2'-3:4)-phenylisobenzopyrylium Perchlorate.—Phenylmagnesium bromide, derived from magnesium (0.04 g.) and bromobenzene (0.23 g.), in ether (10 c.c.) was added to a solution of indenoisocoumarin (0.3 g.) in benzene (5 c.c.), and the mixture left overnight. The sticky yellow complex formed was decomposed with ammonium chloride solution (10 c.c., 20%) and the ethereal layer containing the carbinol was washed with water, dried (MgSO₄), and the solvent removed on a water bath. The gummy residue was treated with a solution of 60% perchloric acid (0.5 c.c.) in acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) with stirring and then dry ether (5 c.c.) was added to the reddish solution. The *pyrylium salt* (0.14 g.) separated in orange-red leaflets, m.p. 245-46° (decomp.). (Found: C, 66.4; H, 3.9. C₂₂H₁₅O₅Cl requires C, 66.9; H, 3.8%).

2-o-Hydroxymethylphenylindan-1-ol (XII).—A suspension of indenoisocoumarin (0.1 g.) in methanol (4 c.c.) was treated with an excess of sodium borohydride (0.3 g.) at the room temperature and the mixture left overnight. After removal of methanol by distillation, the solid residue was treated with dilute acetic acid, and the resulting gummy material was crystallised from benzene.

The *diol* (0.05 g.) separated in colorless prisms, m.p. 132° , raised to $139-40^{\circ}$ on recrystallization. The compound slowly dissolves in H_2SO_4 forming a greenish solution. (Found: C, 80.7; H, 6.6. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 6.7%.)

A solution of 2-*o*-carboxyphenylindan-1-one (0.1 g.; cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*) was reduced with $LiAlH_4$ in ethereal solution. There was no separation of any metal complex. On working up, the product (0.08 g.) crystallised from benzene in colorless prisms; m.p. and mixed m.p. $139-40^{\circ}$.

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